

CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES
DE TRABAJO SOCIAL

ISSN 2244-808X
DL pp 201002Z43506

PERSPECTIVA ACCIÓN Y

Revista de Trabajo Social

Vol. 15 No. 2
Abril - Junio
2025

Universidad del Zulia

Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones en Trabajo Social

Cultura organizacional y bienestar profesional: El papel mediador de la congruencia de valores

Elena Voitenko¹, Ivan Pustovalov², Viktoriia Staryk³, Inna Lapchenko⁴,
Nataliia Hordiienko⁵

¹Department of Psychology, State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, Ukraine.
E-mail: helenmail73@ukr.net; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9407-4574>

²Department of Psychology, State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, Ukraine.
E-mail: v.ivan@knote.edu.ua; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5897-5079>

³Department of Psychology, State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, Ukraine.
E-mail: v.staryk@knote.edu.ua; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5193-6034>

⁴Department of Psychology, State University of Trade and Economics, Kyiv, Ukraine.
E-mail: i.lapchenko@knote.edu.ua; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6573-6789>

⁵Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of Vocational Education, State University
«Kyiv Aviation Institute», Kyiv, Ukraine. E-mail: natali-gordi@ukr.net;
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0688-5626>

Resumen. La congruencia de los valores de la organización y los valores personales de los empleados se considera una condición para preservar su bienestar profesional. El propósito de este estudio es probar empíricamente el papel mediador de la congruencia de valores en la relación entre el tipo percibido de cultura organizacional y el bienestar ocupacional. Se aplicó un método transversal utilizando el Instrumento de Evaluación de Cultura Organizacional (OCAI) de Cameron y Quinn, el Cuestionario de Satisfacción de Necesidades de Porter (NSQ), la Escala de Satisfacción Laboral de Spector (JSS), la Escala de Congruencia de Valores Percibidos del Cuestionario de Congruencia de Valores Personales y Organizacionales para empleados (Q-POVC-115) Vveinhardt & Gulbovaité. Los participantes de la encuesta fueron 92 profesores de escuelas superiores. Los resultados indican que la influencia del tipo percibido de cultura organizacional en el bienestar profesional se lleva a cabo a través de la mediación de la congruencia de valores, que, a su vez, está relacionada con la satisfacción de las necesidades de los empleados. Un entorno congruente con los valores en la organización crea una atmósfera de seguridad psicológica, mejora la interacción, promueve la realización del potencial personal de los empleados y, por lo tanto, contribuye a su bienestar profesional. El efecto mediador revelado por nosotros en la relación

entre las variables estudiadas y el bienestar profesional amplía las ideas existentes sobre el papel de la cultura organizacional en la formación del bienestar profesional de los empleados y abre nuevas perspectivas para la prevención efectiva de sus violaciones.

Palabras clave: cultura organizacional, congruencia de valores, bienestar profesional, bienestar subjetivo, análisis de mediación.

Organizational culture and professional well-being: The mediating role of value congruence

Abstract. The congruence of the organization's values and the personal values of the employees is considered a condition for preserving their professional well-being. The purpose of this study is to empirically test the mediating role of value congruence in the relationship between the perceived type of organizational culture and occupational well-being. A cross-sectional method was applied using Cameron and Quinn's Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI), Porter's Needs Satisfaction Questionnaire (SCN), Spector's Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS), and the Perceived Values Congruence Scale of the Vveinhardt & Gulbovaitė Personal and Organizational Values Congruence Questionnaire for employees (Q-POVC-115). The survey participants were 92 high school teachers. The results indicate that the influence of the perceived type of organizational culture on professional well-being is carried out through the mediation of value congruence, which, in turn, is related to the satisfaction of employee needs. An environment congruent with the values in the organization creates an atmosphere of psychological safety, improves interaction, promotes the realization of employees' personal potential, and thus contributes to their professional well-being. The mediating effect revealed by us in the relationship between the variables studied and professional well-being expands the existing ideas about the role of organizational culture in the formation of employees' professional well-being and opens new perspectives for the effective prevention of their violations.

Key words: organizational culture, congruence of values, professional well-being of the individual, subjective well-being, mediation analysis.

INTRODUCTION

General background information

In the context of the study of organizational and psychological determinants of the professional well-being of an individual, organizational culture is of interest as a potentially influential factor due to its ability to influence all aspects of the organization's activities and the work behavior of employees. Organizational culture influences the high organizational support and the high positive psychological capital (Vasconcelos, Oliveira, & El-Aouar, 2022). It is known that each organization has its own unique organizational culture, which produces values, prescribes and controls the norms of employee interaction, which creates a general psychological climate and unites individual members of the organization into a single organism (Macena, & Bastos, 2020; Petrunko, 2022).

Theorists and practitioners recognize the benefits of engaging employees with organizational values that are congruent with organizational values: it ensures goal-directed and desired behavior of organizational members and contributes to organizational success, positive employee attitudes toward work, and positive organizational climate (Klajkó et al., 2019). The congruence of personal and organizational values means that the organizational values supported by the organization's top management are acceptable to most members of that organization (Vveinhardt, & Gulbovaite, 2018). If the official and unofficial systems of norms and values do not coincide, but contradict each other, this increases the level of emotional tension in the organization. According to the motivational value model of professional well-being (Voitenko et al., 2024), which presents it as an integrated state that is formed in connection with the extent to which individual needs are realized in professional activity, considering individual values and meanings, this fact has a logical explanation. The discrepancy between the organization's values and the employees' personal values prevents the satisfaction of their basic needs, including the need for belonging and autonomy (Ryan, & Deci, 2017), and therefore becomes an obstacle on the way to professional well-being. Employees may feel pressure by working according to goals and values they do not approve of in a so-called "dissonant context" (Rosenberg, 1979), and risk to get less social support, which may affect their sense of belonging. The experience of autonomy also partly depends on the extent to which a person's actions correspond to his own interests and values. Being in the context of dissonant values, the need to act against one's own goals and values reduces the sense of autonomy and, accordingly, becomes an obstacle on the way to professional well-being. Therefore, the congruence of values in organizations is gaining more and more practical importance and determines the need for more well-planned studies of the nature of its relationship with organizational culture and the professional well-being of employees.

Specific background information

Organizational culture and professional well-being

Organizational culture is a relevant area in the context of the study of occupational well-being, as it plays a crucial role in shaping employee behavior. A stable organizational culture is based on a well-defined system of values (Schein, 1975), which determines the style of work of employees, communication and the degree of openness within the organization, their ability to realize their potential and many other everyday organizational practices on which the well-being of employees depends. Organizational culture is viewed as a shared system of beliefs, values, and ways of thinking established by leaders and accepted by all members of an organization (Meng, & Berger, 2019). Organizational values provide a common perception of the organizational climate through the selection and screening of group members, as well as the influence of similar objective characteristics that reinforce similar perceptions. An organization's employees develop a set of mutually acceptable ideas and beliefs about what is important and how to respond, and this increases their engagement and job satisfaction (Meng, & Berger, 2019). Evidence from the literature supports that organizations can enrich their culture with positive elements to create more opportunities to support various aspects of the occupational well-being of their employees. As organizational culture clarifies and establishes the standards of behavior of employees, it improves interaction, communication and mutual respect among them (Lubis and Hanum, 2020) and is considered as a condition for cooperation and performance of organizational members (Shao et al., 2012). Organizational culture can significantly influence perceived stress levels, employee turnover, and organizational identification (Klajkó et al., 2019). However, the relationship between these indicators appears to be mediated

precisely by mutual acceptability, consistency of mutual interests and beliefs, which is emphasized by many researchers as an important condition for the positive functioning of both the organization as a whole and its individual members. It is known, for example, that if the organizational culture meets the requirements of employees, they feel more comfortable and protected in their organization (Bicer, 2022). The concept of cultural fit, formulated in several early studies, assumed that work productivity is a function of the fit between the needs of employees and the culture of the organization, and was recognized as an effective means of increasing employee motivation, job satisfaction, and work engagement. Employees who experience a cultural “misfit” when their needs do not match the needs met by the job are more likely to feel frustrated. For example, unmet needs have been found to be the cause of employee turnover within two to five years (Winter, 1973). Conversely, it has been confirmed that the fit between the type of culture and the needs of employees contributes to job satisfaction and involvement in work processes (Koberg, & Chusmir, 1987). Organizational climates sensitize well-being to a greater extent and women may be able to absorb better the benefits of a friendly and contributory work environment (Macena, & Bastos, 2020). Therefore, the conformity of the organizational environment, first, to the needs of employees, is important for their well-being, health, satisfaction and quality of work.

The impact of value congruence on professional well-being

According to the motivational value model of occupational well-being (Voitenko et al., 2024), meeting needs alone is not enough to achieve occupational well-being. It has been established that the employee evaluates the degree of his well-being based on internal criteria - values that determine the importance of various aspects of professional life and have different effects on the experience of professional well-being. Research in recent decades increasingly examines the congruence of employee and organizational values in the context of its impact on the professional environment and attempts to prove the usefulness of this impact for both employees and organizations. Perceived value congruence refers to a person’s perception of the degree of correspondence, compatibility and similarity of his values with the values of interacting objects (organizations, managers, work groups) (Rahn et al., 2023). It has been established that the perceived congruence of values can positively affect the effectiveness of organizational activities, particularly, reduce resistance to organizational changes on the part of employees, influence the acceptance of these changes (Rahn et al., 2023), helps to stimulate employees’ readiness for organizational changes (Deng et al., 2023), reduces staff turnover (Aldabbas, 2022). One can note an active research interest in the interaction of value congruence with various organizational aspects that directly affect the internal state of employees. It has been found that value congruence can positively influence employee job satisfaction, and conversely, perceived value incongruence is associated with poor well-being and increased risk of burnout (Dunning, et al., 2021). Previous research has shown that value congruence mediates and moderates the relationship between organizational leadership characteristics, particularly leader narcissism and employee defensive behavior (Erkutlu et al., 2020). Congruence of values is considered a key factor in achieving fit between the person and the organization, which reduces stress (Swetha Palla Sai, Padmavathy, 2023). The presence of an employee who matches his organization, team and leader, in turn, acts as a factor of satisfaction on the part of the group leader (Çiçek, & Biçer, 2015): value congruence has a full mediating effect on the relationship between demographic similarity with the leader and his satisfaction, as well as the partial mediating effect between job similarity and leader satisfaction.

Harmonization of individual values and values prevailing in the organization is considered a way to achieve employee cohesion in the organization (Vveinhardt et al., 2016). It has been shown that the congruence of personal and organizational values is related to well-being and perceived achievements at work (Veage et al., 2014). We also have evidence that value congruence influences organizational commitment through the mediation of job happiness (Oyelakin et al., 2021).

Description of the gap in our knowledge that the study was designed to fill

The conducted review revealed a paradox that, on the one hand, confirms that the organizational culture in general and, particularly, the congruence of the values of the organization and employees has a tangible impact on various aspects of the positive functioning of employees, but on the other hand, it is difficult to find studies that would be purposeful studied its relationship with professional well-being. Our research will fill this gap. Studying the mediating role of the congruence of the organization's values and the personal values of employees in the relationship between organizational culture and professional well-being will allow us to form a clearer picture of the nature of the relationships between these variables and open new ways of supporting professional well-being. Based on the conducted analysis, it is possible to assume that the congruence of values mediates the influence of organizational culture on the professional well-being of employees and is related to their needs, and to build a research program based on the following hypotheses:

H1: The perceived type of organizational culture is related to the professional well-being of employees.

H2: Professional well-being of employees is positively correlated with value congruence.

H3: Value congruence is related to employee occupational well-being through the satisfaction of employee needs.

H4: Congruence of values mediates the influence of organizational culture on the professional well-being of employees.

Figure 1 reflects the theoretical basis of the study, according to which the influence of organizational culture on professional well-being is carried out through the mediation of value congruence and the satisfaction of psychological needs of employees.

Figure 1. The mediating effect of value congruence in the relationship between organizational culture and professional well-being.

The study objective

The purpose of this study is to empirically test the mediating role of values congruence in the relationship between the perceived type of organizational culture and the professional well-being of employees.

The article contains the following structural components: the methodological part, which describes the applied methods and diagnostic tools; the next part presents the obtained results, discussion of the results and conclusions.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a continuation of the scientific search for organizational and psychological determinants of professional well-being of an individual, which determined the use of the same methods and, in part, diagnostic tools, described in our previous publication (Voitenko et al., 2024). The purpose of the study was implemented using a cross-sectional method using Porter's Need Satisfaction Questionnaire (NSQ), Spector's Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS), Cameron and Quinn's Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI), Perceived Congruence of Values Questionnaire of the Congruence of Personal and Organizational Values for an Employee (Q-POVC-115) Vveinhardt & Gulbovaite. The study of mediation effects was carried out according to the mediation analysis procedure described by Baron, & Kenny (1986) with preliminary diagnosis of all components. The original scales were translated from English to Ukrainian using the reverse translation method.

To assess the level of satisfaction of employees' needs, the Needs Satisfaction Questionnaire (NSQ) by L. Porter (1961) modified by Roy Payne (Payne, 1970) was used. The questionnaire consists of eight items with a seven-point scale from 1 (minimum) to seven points (maximum). The scale contains three dimensions: the perceived lack of satisfaction of needs (discrepancy score), the indicator of the importance of various aspects of professional activity for the employee (importance score) and the general index of satisfaction of needs (need satisfaction index).

We used Spector's Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) to assess professional well-being (Spector, 2022). The scale determines the employee's attitude to his work according to 9 parameters, and allows to obtain an estimate of overall satisfaction with his position in the organization. Each aspect is assessed on four items, and a total score is calculated for all items. Respondents are offered six answer options for each item ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree".

Organizational culture was measured with the Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI) (Cameron and Quinn, 2011). The questionnaire is designed to determine the current type of culture in the organization, and helps to determine the desired culture, which, according to the members of the organization, should be developed to meet the future demands of the environment and opportunities that the company will face. The questionnaire consists of 24 items related to six key aspects of organizational culture: dominant characteristics, organizational leadership, employee management, organizational "glue", strategic emphasis, success criteria. For each aspect, the four statements reflect four types or profiles of organizational culture: clan, adhocracy, market, and hierarchy. Respondents rated each statement on a scale of 1 to 4, creating a rating in which 1 point was assigned to the statement that they believed best represented their organization.

The Scale of Perceived Congruence of Values from the Questionnaire of Congruence of Personal and Organizational Values for Employees (Q-POVC-115) (Vveinhardt, Gulbovaite, 2018) was used to measure the degrees of perceived correspondence between the values of employees and their organizations. The ultra-short scale contains five items related to the correspondence between the employee's personal values and the values of the organization in which he works, each of which is evaluated on a five-point scale from 1 "completely disagree" to 5 "completely agree".

The participants of this study were 92 academic employees of universities, selected by the method of random selection. The most important socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

Age	N	%	Gender	N	%	Position	N	%
25-35	14	15,2	Male	36	39	Head of Department	22	24
36-45	36	39,1				Lecturer	8	8,7
46-55	26	28,3	Female	56	61	Senior Lecturer	8	8,7
> 56	16	17,4				Associate Professor	42	45,7
Total	92	100		92	100	Professor	12	23,9
							92	100

As can be seen from the data in the table, all age categories and academic positions of the respondents are represented in the study, which confirms the representativeness of the studied sample.

For statistical data processing, correlation analysis and multiple linear regression (MLR) were applied using the enter method without including constants in the equation. The strength and directionality of the relationship between variables was assessed by the parametric linear correlation coefficient of Pearson. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis) were calculated to characterize the observations. The initial data of the variables were checked for compliance with the law of normal distribution. Calculations were performed in SPSS Statistics 23.0.

RESULTS

The presence of statistically significant correlations between the perceived type of organizational culture and the professional well-being of employees was revealed, except for the market culture ($p > .05$), which will be excluded from further analysis, as well as moderate correlations between the perceived type of organizational culture and congruence of values (Table 2).

TABLE 2. The Summary of Descriptive Statistics & Correlations between types of organizational culture, professional well-being and value congruence (N = 92)

Variables	M	SD	S	K	Professional well-being	Value congruence
Clan culture	2,40	,93	,089	-1,18	-,413**	-,351**
Adhocracy culture	2,78	,62	,101	-,842	-,291**	-,226*
Market culture	2,59	,66	-,072	-,928	,100	,117
Culture of hierarchy	2,22	,72	,358	-,839	,274**	-,050
Professional well-being	137,2	20,09	-,546	-,548	1	,612**
Value congruence	15,6	1,6	,007	,410	,612**	1

Note: M - average value; SD – standard deviation; S – skewness; K – kurtosis.

** – correlation statistically significant at the 0.001 level (2-sided).

* – correlation statistically significant at the 0.05 level (2-sided).

The relationship between indicators of need satisfaction, value congruence and professional well-being

To test the hypothesis that the relationship between value congruence and professional well-being functions through the mediation of indicators of satisfaction of individual needs, an analysis of three regression equations was performed (Baron, & Kenny, 1986): first, regression of the mediator (indicators of need satisfaction) on of the independent variable (congruence of values), secondly, regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on the independent variable (congruence of values), thirdly, regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) both on the independent variable (congruence of values) and on the mediator (indicators of satisfaction of needs). Linear regression was applied using the Enter method without including constants in the equation. Significance tests were performed using F-tests, t-tests, adjusted R².

Regression of the mediator (indicators of satisfaction of needs) on the independent variable (congruence of values)

In the first step, the regression of the mediator on the independent variable was estimated (Table 3). The ANOVA test confirmed the reliability of the constructed regression models; therefore, these models can be meaningfully interpreted. Regression analysis confirmed a statistically significant effect of value congruence (VC) on all indicators of need satisfaction according to Porter's Need Satisfaction Questionnaire (NSQ) (1961): Need Satisfaction Index (NSI) ($F=94.612$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.510$), the general indicator of the discrepancy between the desired and the actual state of needs satisfaction (DS) ($F=86.243$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.487$), the general indicator of the importance of the specified aspects of work (IS) ($F=1004.540$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.917$).

Regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on the independent variable (congruence of values)

In the second step, the regression of the dependent variable on the independent variable was estimated (Table 3). A statistically significant effect of value congruence (VC) on overall satisfaction with various aspects of professional activity (PWB) was confirmed ($F=6860.831$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.987$).

Regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) both on the independent variable (congruence of values) and on the mediator (needs)

In the third step, to confirm the influence of the mediator on the dependent variable while controlling for the independent variable, in addition to the need satisfaction indicators, the value congruence indicator was included for the prediction of professional well-being in the regression analysis (Table 3). The model of the joint influence of the predictor and mediator on the dependent variable is statistically significant ($F=1759.580$; $df=4$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.988$), but, as can be seen from the table, the joint influence of value congruence (VC) and indicators of satisfaction of needs on professional well-being is not confirmed ($p>.05$).

TABLE 3. The mediating role of need satisfaction in the relationship between value congruence and professional well-being*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Need Satisfaction Index (NSI)	VC	,010	,001	,714	9,727	,000
	Discrepancy Score (DS)	VC	,063	,007	,698	9,287	,000
	Importance Score (IS)	VC	,365	,012	,958	31,694	,000
2	Professional Wellbeing (PWB)	VC	8,755	,106	,993	82,830	,000
3	Professional Wellbeing (PWB)	VC	8,763	,397	,994	22,100	,000
		DS	-,163	13,567	-,002	-,012	,990
		IS	,730	1,151	,032	,634	,528
		NSI	-26,390	87,532	-,042	-,301	,764

* *Linear Regression through the Origin.*

The model of the third analysis shows that the regression coefficients that demonstrate the contribution of need satisfaction indicators to the variability of professional well-being are statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$), so they can be excluded from the model (table 3). The relative contribution of value congruence to the prediction of professional well-being in this model is 99% ($\beta = .994$), which indicates the practical absence of mediators between these variables.

Correlation analysis of the data confirmed a few linear relationships between the congruence of values and the needs of employees (Table 4).

TABLE 4. The Summary of Descriptive Statistics & Correlations between indicators of need satisfaction and congruence of values (N=92)

Variables	Need for safety	Social needs	Need for respect	Need for autonomy	The need for self-realization	Need Satisfaction Index (NSI)	Discrepancy Score (DS)	Importance Score (IS)
Congruence of values	,27*	,18	,20	,07	,28*	-,50**	-,46**	-,05
Need Satisfaction Index (NSI)	-,26*	-,25*	-,25*	-,04	-,28*	1	,99**	,35**
Discrepancy Score (DS)	-,25*	-,22*	-,21*	-,03	-,22*	,99**	1	,39**
Importance Score (IS)	,56**	,68**	,71**	,79**	,75**	,35**	,39**	1
Statistics								
Mean	4,4	9,4	9,6	5,1	9,5	,16	1,0	5,8
Std. Deviation	1,9	3,4	3,3	1,6	3,5	,15	,97	1,6
Skewness	-,40	-,50	-,72	-1,1	-,73	1,2	1,4	-2,0
Kurtosis	-1,0	-,56	-,31	-,57	-,48	1,7	2,7	2,9

** – correlation statistically significant at the 0.001 level (2-sided)

* – correlation statistically significant at the 0.05 level (2-sided).

The mediating effect of value congruence in the relationship between the perceived type of organizational culture and professional well-being.

To test the assumption that the relationship between the perceived type of organizational culture and professional well-being functions through the mediation of value congruence, three regression equations were analyzed: first, the regression of the mediator (value congruence) on the independent variable (organizational culture), second, the regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on the independent variable (organizational culture), third, the regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on both the independent variable (organizational culture) and the mediator (value congruence). Linear regression was applied using the Enter method without including constants in the equation. Significance tests were performed using F-tests, t-tests, adjusted R2.

Regression of the mediator (congruence of values) on the independent variable (organizational culture)

At the first stage, the regression of the mediator on the independent variable was estimated (table 5). Regression analysis confirmed a statistically significant influence of the perceived type of organizational culture on value congruence: clan culture (CC) ($F=475.259$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.839$), culture of adhocracy (CA) ($F=1278.737$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.934$), hierarchy culture (CH) ($F=772.006$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.895$).

TABLE 5. Regression of the mediator (congruence of values) on the independent variable (organizational culture)*

Models	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 Clan Culture (CC) VC	,150	,007	,916	21,800	,000
2 Culture of Adhocracy (CA) VC	,175	,005	,966	35,759	,000
3 Culture of Hierarchy (CH) VC	,140	,005	,946	27,785	,000

*Linear Regression through the Origin.

Regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on the independent variable (organizational culture)

At the second stage, the regression of the dependent variable on the independent variable was estimated (table 6). A statistically significant influence of the perceived type of organizational culture on the professional well-being of employees was confirmed: clan culture (CC) ($F=397.896$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.814$), culture of adhocracy (CA) ($F=980.999$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.915$), hierarchy culture (CH) ($F=925.028$; $df=1$; $p<0.001$; $R^2=.910$).

TABLE 6. Regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on the independent variable (organizational culture)*

Models			Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Clan Culture (CC)	PWB	48,659	2,439	,902	19,947	,000
2	Culture of Adhocracy (CA)	PWB	46,631	1,489	,957	31,321	,000
3	Culture of Hierarchy (CH)	PWB	56,605	1,861	,954	30,414	,000

**Linear Regression through the Origin.*

Regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on both the independent variable (organizational culture) and the mediator (value congruence)

At the third stage, to confirm the influence of the mediator on the dependent variable while controlling the independent variable, in addition to value congruence, the perceived type of organizational culture is included in the regression models to predict the professional well-being of employees (Table 7). The ANOVA test confirmed the reliability of the constructed regression models; therefore, these models can be meaningfully interpreted. The joint influence of value congruence (VC) and clan culture (CC) ($R^2=.987$; $F=3499.749$; $df=2$; $p<0.001$), value congruence (VC) and culture of adhocracy (CA) ($R^2=.987$; $F=3435.027$; $df=2$; $p<0.001$), values congruence (VC) and hierarchy culture ($R^2=.989$; $df=2$; $p<0.001$).

TABLE 7. Regression of the dependent variable (professional well-being) on both the independent variable (organizational culture) and the mediator (value congruence)*

Model			Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
			B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Professional well-being	Clan Culture (CC)	-2,675	1,598	-,050	-1,674	,098
		Value Congruence (VC)	9,155	,261	1,039	35,066	,000
2	Professional well-being	Culture of Adhocracy (CA)	-2,386	2,267	-,049	-1,052	,295
		Value Congruence (VC)	9,171	,410	1,041	22,379	,000
3	Professional well-being	Culture of hierarchy (CH)	8,197	2,027	,138	4,044	,000
		Value Congruence (VC)	7,603	,301	,863	25,253	,000

**Linear Regression through the Origin.*

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to determine the nature of the relationship between organizational culture, value congruence, needs and professional well-being of employees, and, particularly, to empirically test the mediating role of value congruence in the relationship between the perceived type of organizational culture and professional well-being. Correlation analysis revealed the presence of statistically significant moderate correlations between indicators of clan culture ($r=-.413$; $p<.001$),

adhocracy culture ($r=-.291$; $p<.001$) and hierarchy culture ($r=.274$; $p<.001$) and professional well-being of employees. Market culture does not have a linear relationship with professional well-being ($r=.100$; $p>.05$). Our findings of negative correlations of clan culture and adhocracy culture with employee well-being are inconsistent with previous research that found that clan culture exhibits the strongest positive correlation with job satisfaction, followed by adhocracy, hierarchy, and market cultures (Aldhuwaihi, Shee and Stanton, 2012; Olynick, & Li, 2020). Employees working in clan cultures reported the lowest levels of stress, followed by adhocracy, hierarchy, and market cultures (Klajkó et al., 2019; Olynick, & Li, 2020). At first glance, these are logical and expected connections: clan culture is characterized by teamwork, consensus and participation, emphasizes human resource development, facilitation and mentoring by the leader (Basar et al., 2022), which together determine the success of such an organization. The culture of adhocracy is focused on entrepreneurship, innovation, creativity, and risk-taking, with personal development as the highest priority (Sherman et al., 2014). Our revealed results become more understandable considering the obtained negative correlations between clan cultures ($r=-.351$; $p<.001$) and adhocracy ($r=-.226$; $p<.05$) with the level of congruence of values of employees and organizations in which they work and are obviously related to the specifics of the studied sample and its value priorities. In contrast to previous studies, the participants of which were employed in various sectors of work at the university, including maintenance, library services, health care, etc. (Olynick, & Li, 2020), our study sample was homogenous and represented purely by academic staff. A high school teacher is an ambitious individual motivated to achieve, first, individual success, so teamwork and coordination in a clan culture can be a cause of dissatisfaction due to a lack of autonomy. Under the conditions of the adhocracy culture, the organization is a very dynamic and entrepreneurial environment that requires readiness for risk and new challenges. All this obviously contradicts the desire of employees for order, stability, freedom from stress, that is, the desire for psychological safety, which is an important aspect of the well-being of employees (Voitenko et al., 2023). In this sense, the positive correlation of hierarchy culture with occupational well-being is logical given its ability to provide stability, predictability and security for employees (Basar et al., 2022). The market culture, focused on increasing the productivity of the organization, results and getting ahead of competitors, is characterized by high demands on employees and, accordingly, high stressogenicity (Klajkó et al., 2019), therefore it does not correlate with the professional well-being of employees focused on stability and safety. Thus, the results generally support our hypothesis, which predicted differences in the relationship between perceived types of organizational culture and employee occupational well-being.

Correlation analysis confirmed the hypothesis of a positive relationship between the congruence of the values of employees and the organization and professional well-being ($r=.612$; $p<.001$). This result is in good agreement with the data of previous studies, which also confirmed the impact of the congruence of the values on various aspects of professional well-being, in particular, its positive impact on employee job satisfaction (Dunning et al., 2021); impact on well-being and perceived achievement at work (Veage et al., 2014).

The results of the analysis of the mediating effect of indicators of satisfaction of needs on the relationship between the congruence of values and the professional well-being of employees are shown in Table 3. Mediator analysis shows that the relationship between value congruence and professional well-being does not function through the mediation of indicators of satisfaction of individual needs. The results showed that the regression coefficients, which demonstrate the contribution of need satisfaction indicators to the variability of professional well-being, lost statistical significance ($p>.05$)

after entering them into the study as a mediator, so they can be excluded from the model. The relative contribution of value congruence to the prediction of professional well-being in this model is 99% ($\beta=.994$), which indicates the practical absence of mediators between these variables.

Correlation analysis of the data confirmed a few linear relationships between the congruence of values and the needs of employees (Table 4). The current state of satisfaction of needs according to L. Porter's scale reflects the resources of the organization that meet the needs of employees. As can be seen from Table 4, a high level of value congruence is associated with a high sense of security ($r=.273$; $p<0.05$). This is a logical and expected relationship based on the definition of value congruence (Vveinhardt, & Gulbovaite, 2018). If official and unofficial value systems contradict each other, this increases the level of conflict and emotional tension in the organization and, accordingly, threatens the psychological safety of employees. Congruence of values correlates with social needs and the need for respect at the level of a statistical trend ($p<0.1$), which raises some doubts about accepting the hypothesis that there is no connection between these variables. Employees risk less social support when working in a so-called "dissonant context" (Rosenberg, 1979), which may affect their desire for belonging. The theoretically expected correlation of value congruence with the need for autonomy was not established ($p>0.05$). Congruence of values positively correlates with the existing state of satisfaction of the need for self-realization at the level of statistical significance ($r=.276$; $p<0.05$), which is explained by the fact that an employee who effectively satisfies the need for self-realization is characterized by acceptance of himself and the surrounding environment, a feeling involvement and unity with others (Maslow, 1970). Congruence of values correlates with the indicator of the discrepancy between the desired and actual state of needs satisfaction (DS) ($r=-.459$; $p<.001$) and the needs satisfaction index (NSI) at a high level of statistical significance ($r=-.496$; $p<.001$). The importance indicator, which in the applied modification of the scale is an auxiliary indicator designed to determine the Need Satisfaction Index, does not correlate with the congruence of values ($p>0.05$). The obtained results show that a high level of value congruence correlates with a low level of discrepancy between the desired and actual states of satisfaction of the needs of employees. The relationship with the generalized needs satisfaction index (NSI) has a negative modality due to the specificity of its calculation. The need satisfaction index (NSI) is obtained by dividing the total discrepancy score (DS) by the total importance rating for the employee of the selected aspects of the job (IS). NSI can range from "0" to "1", with need satisfaction being higher as the index approaches "0". Therefore, an increase in value congruence is associated with an increase in the level of satisfaction of employees' needs.

The results of the mediation analysis of value congruence in the relationship between the perceived type of organizational culture and professional well-being confirmed the assumption that value congruence mediates the influence of organizational culture on the professional well-being of employees. Full mediation by the congruence of values of the impact of clan culture ($\beta=1.039$) and adhocracy culture ($\beta=1.041$) on professional well-being was statistically confirmed. Regression coefficients that demonstrate the contribution of indicators of clan culture and adhocracy culture to the variability of professional well-being lost statistical significance ($p>0.05$) after inclusion in the study of congruence of values as a mediator, which indicates the existence of a single dominant mediator (Baron, & Kenny, 1986). This result is in good agreement with the results of previous studies, which also confirmed the mediating role of values in the achievement of occupational well-being by employees (Voitenko et al., 2024). The obtained results revealed a partial mediation by the congruence of values of the influence of hierarchy culture on the pro-

professional well-being of employees. As can be seen from the data in Table 6, the joint influence of values congruence and hierarchy culture on professional well-being is statistically confirmed. The results showed that the relationship between hierarchy culture and occupational well-being remained statistically significant when value congruence measures were entered into the study as a mediator. The share of the variation in professional well-being is explained by the variation in the level of psychological safety and indicators of satisfaction of needs for almost 99% ($R^2=.989$) and only 1% is explained by other factors. A comparison of the regression coefficients shows that the effect of hierarchy culture on occupational well-being was significantly reduced in the third equation ($\beta=.138$) than in the second ($\beta=.954$), after value congruence measures were added as a mediator. A significant reduction in the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable indicates that the mediator is indeed powerful (Baron, & Kenny, 1986). Therefore, it can be concluded that the connection between organizational culture and professional well-being functions through the mediation of value congruence, which in turn is related to the satisfaction of the employee's needs. Each employee experiences professional well-being in the context of personal values and needs, the possibility of realizing which in professional activity depends on consistency with organizational values.

CONCLUSIONS

The conducted research showed that the way employees perceive their work environment and, particularly, the organizational culture, is important for their professional well-being. The obtained results made it possible to confirm the existence of a connection between the perceived type of organizational culture and the professional well-being of employees. It was established that the directionality of this connection depends on the specific characteristics of the organizational culture. Indicators of clan culture and culture of adhocracy have moderate negative correlations with professional well-being, indicators of hierarchy culture have a positive relationship with professional well-being. Market culture does not have a linear relationship with professional well-being. Considering the obtained negative correlations between clan and adhocracy cultures with the level of congruence of values of employees and the organizations in which they work, it can be concluded that the relationship between organizational culture and professional well-being is related to the value priorities of the studied sample, in particular congruence of the organization's values with the personal values of employees.

It has been confirmed that the congruence of the values of the organization and employees is an important determinant of their professional well-being due to its connection with needs. Congruence of values has a linear relationship with the existing state of satisfaction of the needs of employees, in particular, the need for safety and self-realization, as well as with social needs and the need for respect at the level of a statistical trend. Congruence of values correlates with generalized indicators of employee satisfaction at a high level of statistical significance. Mediator analysis confirmed that value congruence is the dominant mediator between the perceived type of organizational culture and the professional well-being of employees. Value congruence has a full mediating effect on the relationship between clan culture and occupational well-being and adhocracy culture and occupational well-being, and a partial mediating effect between hierarchy culture and occupational well-being. Therefore, the influence of organizational culture on the professional well-being of employees is mediated by the consistency of their values with the values of the organization, which, in

turn, is related to the satisfaction of employees' needs. A value-congruent environment creates an atmosphere of psychological safety, improves interaction, promotes the realization of the personal potential of employees, and therefore contributes to their professional well-being.

The mediating effect revealed by us in the relationship between the studied variables and professional well-being expands the existing ideas about the role of organizational culture in the formation of the professional well-being of employees and opens new perspectives for the effective prevention of its violations. The search for practical ways to achieve congruence of values in the organization should be the direction of further research.

The limitation of this study concerns, firstly, the somewhat limited number of the studied sample. Secondly, the survey was conducted in several universities. The participants were asked to voluntarily take part in the survey, but the verification of voluntary participation, as well as the complete exclusion of administrative influence, appears to be impossible. These conditions may have somewhat influenced the generalized results.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Aldabbas, H. (2022). "Antecedents and consequences of perceived insider status and suggestions for future research". *Journal of positive school psychology*, 6(10), 2813-2832. <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/13761/8920>
- Aldhuwaihi A., Shee H., and Stanton P. (2012). "World. Organisational Culture and the Job Satisfaction-Turnover Intention Link: A Case Study of the Saudi Arabian Banking Sector". *Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 127 – 141. <https://vuir.vu.edu.au/id/eprint/22803>
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). "The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations". *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173>
- Basar, P. & Ilkan, E. & Mutair, F. (2022). "Cameron and Quinn's model of organizational culture: a case study in CAC Bank". *Journal of Organizational Behavior Research*, 7(2), 259-266. <https://doi.org/10.51847/NsL9E5rPjr>.
- Biçer C. (2022). "Organizational Culture". In: *Academic comments and analyzes on developments in finance and economics*, Ankara: Ekin Yayınevi, 205-214
- Cameron, K.S. and Quinn, R.E. (2011). "Diagnosing and Changing Organisational Culture Based on Competing Values Framework". 3rd edition. Josey Bass, San Francisco.
- Çiçek, I., & Biçer, İ. H. (2015). "Mediating Role of Value Congruence on the Relationship between Relational Demography and Satisfaction from Team Leader: A Research in Technology-based Organization". *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 181, 33-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.863>
- Deng, J., Cheng, Z., Qi, S., & Deng, R. (2023). "Unravelling the relationship between perceived values-congruence with organizational change readiness: A moderated mediation model". *Frontiers in psychology*, 14, 1086326. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1086326>
- Dunning, A., Louch, G., Grange, A., Spilsbury, K., & Johnson, J. (2021). "Exploring nurses' experiences of value congruence and the perceived relationship with wellbeing and patient care and safety: a qualitative study". *Journal of research in nursing*, 26(1-2), 135-146. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120976172>

- Erkutlu, Hakan & Bektas, Haci & Chafra, Jamel Ben. (2020). "Leader Narcissism and Defensive Silence in Higher Education: A Moderated Mediation Model of Interactional Justice and Value Congruence". *Research in Educational Administration & Leadership*, 5, 586-622. <https://doi.org/10.30828/real/2020.2.9>.
- Klajkó, Dóra & Restás, Péter & Szabó, Zsolt & Czibor, Andrea. (2019). "The effect of organizational culture on employee well-being: work-related stress, employee identification, turnover intention". *Journal of international cooperation and development*, 2(2), 19-35. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jicd-2019-0010>
- Koberg, C. S., & Chusmir, L. H. (1987). "Organizational culture relationships with creativity and other job-related variables". *Journal of Business Research*, 15(5), 397-409. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963\(87\)90009-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0148-2963(87)90009-9)
- Lubis, F. R., & Hanum, F. (2020, December). "Organizational culture". In Proceedings of the 2nd Yogyakarta International Conference on Educational Management/Administration and Pedagogy (YICEMAP 2019) (pp. 88-91). Atlantis Press.
- Macena, L. F. C., & Bastos, S. A. P. (2020). "The Impact of Human Resource Practices on Organizational Climate and Employee Well-Being". *Management and Business Research Quarterly*, 15, 11-28. <https://doi.org/10.32038/mbrq.2020.15.02>
- Maslow, A.H. (1970). "Motivation and personality". New York: Harper & Row.
- Meng, J., & Berger, B. K. (2019). "The impact of organizational culture and leadership performance on PR professionals' job satisfaction: Testing the joint mediating effects of engagement and trust". *Public Relations Review*, 45(1), 64-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2018.11.002>
- Olynick, J. & Li, H. (2020). "Organizational Culture and Its Relationship with Employee Stress, Enjoyment of Work and Productivity". *International Journal of Psychological Studies*. 12(2). 14-30. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijps.v12n2p14>.
- Oyelakin, O., Shodeinde, A. D. & Arandong, I. J. (2021). "Value Congruence and Organizational Commitment: Does Work Happiness Matter?". *Business Perspective Review*, 3(2), 14-26. <https://doi.org/10.38157/businessperspective-review.v3i2.348>
- Payne R. (1970). "Factor analysis of a maslow-type need satisfaction questionnaire". *Personnel Psychology*, 23(2), 251-268. <https://doi:10.1111/j.1744-6570.1970.tb01654.x>
- Petrunko O.V.(2022) "Orhanizatsiina kultura universytetu yak chynnyk yoho konkurentozdatnosti na rynku osvitynih posluh" [Organizational culture of the university as a factor of its competitiveness in the market of educational services.]. *Vcheni zapysky Universytetu «KROK»*, 1(65), 64-175 [In Ukrainian]
- Porter, L.W.(1961). "A study of perceived need satisfaction in bottom and middle management jobs". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 45, 1-10. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/h0043121>
- Quinn, R. and Spreitzer, G. (1991). "The Psychometric of the Competing Values Culture Instrument and an Analysis of the Impact of Organizational Culture on Quality of Life". In: Woodman, R.W. and Pasmore, W.A., Eds., *Research in Organizational Change and Development*, 5, JAI Press, Greenwich, 115-142
- Rahn, O. G., Soutar, G. N., & Lee, J. A. (2023). "Perceived values-congruence and employees' change beliefs". *Journal of Management & Organization*, 29(6), 991-1009. <https://doi:10.1017/jmo.2020.4>
- Rosenberg, M. (1979). "Conceiving the self". Basic Books.

- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). "Self-Determination Theory: Basic Psychological Needs in Motivation, Development, and Wellness". Guilford Press.
- Schein, E. H. (1975). "In defense of theory Y". *Organizational Dynamics*, 4(1), 17–30. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616\(75\)90002-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0090-2616(75)90002-9).
- Shao, Z., Feng, Y. and Liu, L. (2012). "The mediating effect of organizational culture and knowledge sharing on transformational leadership and Enterprise Resource Planning systems success: An empirical study in China". *Computers in Human Behavior*, 28, 2400-2413. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1016/j.chb.2012.07.011>
- Sherman, S. G., Leahy, M. J., Del Valle, R., Anderson, C. A., Tansey, T. N., & Lui, K. (2014). "Organizational and cultural factors that promote creative best practices in the public rehabilitation program: Findings from a four-state multiple case study". *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation*, 41(2), 115–125. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2014-38843-003>
- Spector, P. E. (2022). "Job satisfaction: From Assessment to Intervention". New York City: Routledge.
- Swetha Palla Sai, Padmavathy G. (2023). "Value congruence: A fit between personal and organizational values". *International Journal of Advance Research and Development*, 3(12), 28-32. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31966.61761>.
- Vasconcelos, C. R. M., de Oliveira, H. C. C., & El-Aouar, W. A. (2022). "Organizational Culture, Organizational Support, and Positive Psychological Capital: Validation of a Theoretical Model". *International Journal of Behavior Studies in Organizations*, 7, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.32038/JBSO.2022.07.01>
- Veage S., Ciarrochi J., Deane F., Andresen R., Oades L., Crowe T. (2014). "Value congruence, importance and success and in the workplace: Links with well-being and burnout amongst mental health practitioners", *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 3(4), 258-264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcbs.2014.06.004>
- Voitenko, E., Myronets, S., Timchenko O., Yakymchuk B., Skrypkin O. (2023). "A cross-cultural comparison of perception of professional well-being by Iranian and Ukrainian academic staff". *International journal of organizational leadership*. 12 (First Special Issue-2023). 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.33844/ijol.2023.60351>
- Voitenko, E., Zazymko, O., Myronets, S., Staryk, V., & Kushnirenko, K. (2024). "The mediating role of values in the relationship between needs and professional well-being of university academic staff". *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 13(1), 102-116. <https://doi.org/10.33844/ijol.2024.60401>
- Vveinhardt, J., & Gulbovaite, E. (2018). "Reliability of methodological and psychometric characteristics of the questionnaire of congruence of personal and organizational values". *Oeconomia Copernicana*, 9(3), 545–571. <https://doi.org/10.24136/oc.2018.028>
- Vveinhardt, J., Gulbovaite, E., Streimikiene, D. (2016). "Values congruence from the executives' viewpoint: value-based practices, economics and sociology", 9(2), 248-265. <https://doi.org/10.14254/2071-789X.2016/9-2/17>
- Winter, D. G. (1973). "The Power Motive". The Free Press, New York.